

ENGAGING CITIZENS IN SOIL SCIENCE:
THE ROAD TO HEALTHIER SOILS

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The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

This document is a public deliverable (D6.1) and as such will be available online with unrestricted access. It outlines the ECHO project's overall approach to communication, dissemination and exploitation - part of WP6: Dissemination and Communication. Although the Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan is a deliverable to be submitted to the European Commission by month 4 of the ECHO project, it will be annually reviewed and updated to ensure that its objectives are met and amended if necessary.

The C&D&E Plan is designed to provide consortium partners the required support in approaching a unitary and consistent style of communication regarding the project and its related activities.

Communication and dissemination activities are directed towards raising awareness among the target groups, engaging stakeholders and promoting the project together with related activities, achievements and potential exploitation perspectives.

The C&D&E Plan includes a specific set of both dissemination measures (for the public disclosure of project results and transfer of knowledge to key citizen groups) and communication activities (targeted measures to promote the project, activities to engage citizens and end-users, information about the project's contribution towards societal challenges).

The specific objectives of this document are to:

- Determine the goals of the C&D&E Strategy
- Identify target groups to which the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities are addressed
- Design an action plan to communicate and disseminate the activities and exploit of results of ECHO
- Select adequate channels, tools and media to support these activities
- Provide monitoring implementation metrics to assess the progress, performance, and success of the dissemination and communication action plan.

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Foreword

Soil is a vital, yet often disregarded, resource that supports life on Earth by providing the foundation for agriculture, forests, and various other natural ecosystems. However, soil degradation is a growing concern around the world, and it can have severe consequences for our planet like reduced crop yields, increased greenhouse gas emissions, and decreased biodiversity. The ECHO project aims to prevent this by bringing together citizens and volunteer scientists from around Europe to work towards a common goal of protecting and preserving our soils, thus contributing to the transition towards healthy soils of the EU Mission: “A Soil Deal for Europe”.

ECHO will generate new data on the health status of EU soils, complementing existing soil mapping and monitoring in EU Member States and Scotland, including the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO). The project will develop and deploy 28 tailor-made citizen science initiatives across EU Member States and Scotland, taking into account different land-uses, soil types, and biogeographical regions, as well as stakeholder needs. With 16 participants from all over Europe, including 10 leading universities and research centres, 4 SMEs, and 2 Foundations, under the coordination of the Free University of Bolzano-Bozen, ECHO will assess 16,500 sites in different climate and biogeographic regions to achieve its ambitious goals.

The project aims to engage citizens in protecting and restoring soils by building their capacities and enhancing their knowledge. Citizens will thereby not only actively contribute to the project’s data collection but also promote soil stewardship and foster behavioural change across the EU. The ECHOREPO, a long-term open access repository with a direct link to the EUSO, will make the citizen science data available for exploitation not only by scientists but also by citizens, policy makers, farmers, landowners and other end-users, providing added value to existing data and other relevant soil monitoring initiatives. ECHOREPO will thus provide valuable information about the state of soil health in various regions, and help citizens make informed decisions about land use and conservation.

We believe that the ECHO project will have a significant impact on soil health and citizen engagement across Europe and become an important step towards protecting and preserving our soil for future generations. By working together, we can ensure that our soil remains healthy and productive, and that we continue to enjoy the many benefits it provides.

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1. Communication

1.1 Scope and objectives

Communication is key in supporting the technical activities of any project, and remains important throughout the entire lifespan of the project. ECHO's communication strategy is therefore in synergy with the main goal of the project, i.e., to enhance existing, and create new, knowledge through the amplification of novel scientific research and increasing awareness and literacy of soil health related issues throughout Europe and beyond. Communication will take place during all project phases between months 1 to 48. Table 1 summarizes the communication objectives.

ECHO - Engaging citizens in soil science: the road to healthier soils is a project for which citizen science is the main approach to engage, enable and empower citizens. Citizen science projects rely on public involvement, making communication and dissemination essential to their success and impact. Citizen science projects must expand beyond traditional top-down monologue and embrace two-way dialogue approaches, especially when communicating with project participants. The project has to actively communicate with potential target groups and spark their interest in contributing to data collection. There is not one perfect solution to effective communication in citizen science, as there are many factors in our project that must be taken into account.

To enhance the engagement of citizen scientists and increase the understanding and awareness of the importance of soils, ECHO will run **28 co-creation workshops** involving up to **16500 citizens**. Citizens involved in ECHO will be able to value the crucial role soils play in their daily life.

Project partners should actively communicate the project outside the scientific community, to increase visibility, raise awareness, and stimulate participation. In order to achieve this goal they are encouraged to keep the content accessible and understandable for project's target groups. The key messaging of the project will be available in all of the partners' native languages.

The communication activities of ECHO aim to create high-performing active communities, enhance public awareness, knowledge and literacy of the importance of soils, and increasing the soil scientific literacy and the openness of soil research whilst promoting soil stewardship on a pan-European level. A mixture of communication means, media and activities are envisioned to reach a broad portfolio of target and stakeholder groups. A common visual identity is adopted to synchronise communication activities by ECHO partners. Key messages to be communicated (beyond the benefits of our solutions and the specific project results) comprise the collaborative, cross-disciplinary and international nature of the project, its added value in terms of policy, scientific and innovative outputs and its funding (e.g., creation of a data repository that integrates with existing EU infrastructure such as EUSO), as well as its joint, integrative focus on societal, ecological, and economic aspects central to multiple UN sustainable development goals.

Table 1. Communication objectives.

General objective	Specific objectives
Design the visual identity to synchronise communication activities by ECHO partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a logo to make the project easily recognizable • Create other necessary elements of visual identification used in communication: word template, presentation slide, banner, leaflet
Develop necessary tools to support an effective dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a project website: www.echosoil.eu • Create social media channels (LinkedIn, FB) - to reach a diverse audience and engage with them • Create a leaflet with key information about the project to be distributed during events, workshops, online, etc. • Provide ECHO Partners with the Project Communication and Visibility Toolbox, to assist them in implementing transparent communication activities within the ECHO project
Create high-performing active communities at local, national and European levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use social media channels (LinkedIn, FB) to engage with stakeholders and maximise communication opportunities • Issue a newsletter periodically to keep stakeholders informed • Participate in webinars, conferences, and workshops to identify and connect with a wider range of stakeholders • Engage with other European projects related to ECHO to cooperate in dissemination activities
Disseminate the project activities and messages in relevant events and congresses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate actively in research and related other events and conferences. • Newsletters of project outcomes – 6-monthly • Organize co-creation workshops and training sessions for citizens and end-users

1.2 Preliminary analysis

Before starting the communication strategy of ECHO - as a new project - it was necessary to analyse the resources and communication channels of ECHO partners. This is needed to decide which existing channels we can use and link them with new project tools, and therefore ECHO can multiply the impact of actions of each ECHO communication channel by benefiting from the outreach of the project partners' channels.

1.3 Target Groups

The key to a successful communication strategy is a good understanding of target groups (Table 2) to which we send project messages (Table 4). Different target groups have been identified to support the development of specific messages and channels. In addition, as part of the activity of *Task 3.1. Mapping and engaging target citizen groups* within WP3 and the related deliverable (D3.1 Report on identified communities of stakeholders and engagement), we will further summarize all the possible target groups and key stakeholder communities identified to engage them in the project.

Target groups include members of citizen science initiatives, youth groups and organisations, women's groups and organisations, farmers organisations, forestry organisations, environmental conservation groups and associations (including NGOs), urban food and growing associations, city greening initiatives, members (in a volunteer base) of local and regional authorities.

ECHO will utilise different means to approach identified citizen groups. These will include:

- i. targeted dissemination of project materials through press releases shared online and through traditional channels, and social media;
- ii. online (if possible, face-to-face) one-to-one meetings with group representatives;
- iii. creation of a calendar of activities, including interactive workshops and targeted presentations, promoted online (through social media, e-mail, and the project website).

Table 2. ECHO outcomes, target groups and tools to reach them

Outcomes	Target groups	How to reach them
Significantly increased public's awareness of the value of soil.	Students, student associations, youth groups and organisations, scientists, NGOs, farmers and other land-managers, landowners, farmer/forester consultant agencies, educational institutions, farmer and forest associations, urban food and growing associations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Social media • Promotional materials • Online (if possible, face-to-face) one-to-one meetings with group representatives • Events
Citizens are empowered to take an active role in science and in increasing the knowledge base on soils. by monitoring and gathering data on soil biodiversity and becoming more aware of the importance of soils and the soil food web in their daily lives.	Students, student associations, youth groups and organisations, scientists, NGOs, farmers and other land-managers, landowners, farmer/forester consultant agencies, educational institutions, farmer and forest associations, urban food and growing associations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Social media • Promotional materials • Online (if possible, face-to-face) one-to-one meetings with group representatives • Co-creation workshops • Targeted presentations
Greater availability of local scale data on soil health. This will expand and complement established soil databases to support critical landscape decisions and policy development.	scientists, researchers, farmers, foresters, land managers, farmer/forester consultant agencies, educational institutions, governmental authorities, decision makers, national health/environmental authorities, conservation and biodiversity authorities, NGOs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Newsletter • Promotional materials • Press releases • Conferences • Publications

The EU Soil Observatory scope is enlarged and populated with citizen science data.	scientists, researchers, farmers, foresters, land managers, farmer/forester consultant agencies, educational institutions, governmental authorities, decision makers, national health/environmental authorities, conservation and biodiversity authorities, NGOs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Newsletter • Press releases • Conferences • Publications
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1.5 Key channels and activities

The main communication channels to be used for communication are the following:

- Project website and social media channels
- Direct emailing
- Press releases, articles and newsletter
- Printed and digital materials: leaflet, banners, videos
- Conference presentation

A detailed outline of the tools, channels and related **KPIs** are listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Tools, Channels and KPIs for dissemination and communication activities

Tool	Channel	KPI
ECHO website with Citizen Science Platform	Internet	> 15000 visitors and page views
Press releases to announce the start of the project and the specific events of ECHO (e.g. co-creation workshops)	LinkedIn, Facebook, Website, local newspaper, and other local media	4 press releases for the duration of the project; > 800 FB followers; > 300 subscribed to LinkedIn
Newsletter to report on project updates	Website, mailing list	2 newsletter/year, totalling 500 views each
Videos - short clips for social media sharing, presenting key issues of soil health (e.g. video on importance of soil biodiversity), methods to assess soil health,	YouTube, project webpage, social media	Release of 2 videos (2-3 minutes) and 4 shorter clips (60 seconds), 100 000 views of each video for the duration of the project – main language will be English with subtitles in all official EU languages
Continuous social media posting	Website, social media	10 posts/month
Presentations	Conferences and events	Number of events attended: 10 per year

Articles	Specialized and mainstream media, scientific journals	Number of articles: 8 scientific papers, 2 outreach articles/year written also in local language
Webinars	Video conference platforms (zoom, teams, google meet)	Number of participants: at least >40 attendees/event.
Brochures and flyers	Events	Total distribution: >1000

1.5 Key messages

Communication with stakeholders will be based on key messages constructed to convey, in the most comprehensive way, relevant information from the perspective of such stakeholders. Table 4 illustrates some examples of key messages to use when communicating to stakeholders.

Table 4. ECHO key messages

Target group	Message
Students, student associations, youth groups and organisations, women's groups and organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil is a vital, yet often disregarded, resource that supports life on Earth by providing the foundation for agriculture, forests, and various other natural ecosystems. Soil performs functions essential for life. • Take the step towards protecting and preserving our soil for future generations. • Find out, how you can lead the transition toward healthy soils with ECHO.
Farmers organisations, forestry organisations, environmental conservation groups and associations (including NGOs), urban food and growing associations, city greening initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil is a non-renewable resource that needs to be maintained and protected through adoption of sustainable soil-friendly practices • ECHO is generating knowledge which “make the invisible visible” allowing soils to reach the same importance in society as water and air. • By working together, we can ensure that our soil remains healthy and productive for future generations.
Academia - scientists, researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ECHO is providing experimental data and support for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. • Being open-access and compatible with established soil databases and ongoing European soil monitoring programs, ECHO will give a substantial added value at European scale.

Decision makers - local and regional authorities, governmental authorities, national health/environmental authorities, conservation and biodiversity authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ECHO is providing access to data that will enable and improve effective decision making to protect and improve soil health.
General public & Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ECHO will enable citizens to understand the vital role of soils and their individual impact on soil and empower them to actively contribute to soil friendly practices, including their consumer choice that in turn may leverage improved supply chain engagement on soils. Healthy soil means healthy food.

1.6 Branding and tools

1.6.1 Logo

Project's logo consists of the word ECHO placed underground, sprouting into four, echoing plants in vibrant shades of green. It evokes both the importance of soil, and the nourishment it provides to all living things.

ECHO logo

Our chosen fonts:

Calibri, Catallina - clean, modern, elegant

The logo will be included in all project communication, dissemination and promotional materials of the project.

1.6.2 Project website

We believe that project's website can be an effective tool, aiding us in reaching our target audiences.

The ECHO's website was created as **Deliverable 6.2**, part of WP6 Dissemination and Communication. Its goal is not only to inform and promote. ECHO's website will host the public dissemination deliverables, the Citizen Science platform including the toolbox and mobile app (WP2) and will be link to the ECHOREPO digital repository (WP5).

Address: **echosoil.eu** - short, memorable and descriptive

Availability: Up to six years from the start of the project, exceeding the lifetime of the project

Language: The main content of the website will be in English, with summary information, project abstract, main outcomes translated in the languages covered by the project consortium (Italian, German, French, Spanish, Portuguese, Greek, Finnish, Polish, Romanian).

The website is divided into the following sections: ABOUT (which links to the home page), PARTNERS, NEWS & EVENTS, RESOURCES and CONTACT. Our slogan - Engaging citizens in soil science: the road to healthier soils - is also featured in the main menu.

ECHO will also develop open-source, easy-to-understand training materials, which will be displayed on the project's website. Training materials will allow easy adoption and use of the Citizen Science toolbox and will include video guides on how to use the different components of the toolbox; instructions on how to package and send soil samples to an ECHO lab for off-site assessments; instructions and protocols on how to perform on-site assessments. Furthermore, the comprehensive materials will include a territorial guide on the main soil uses across Europe, as well as a description of each of the eight soil health indicators used within ECHO. All materials developed in this subtask will be translated into the official languages of the EU.

All Partners and participants are welcome and encouraged to put the project website address on all printed items, press releases, paper and electronic correspondence, etc, include a link to the project's website on their pages and ask other relevant stakeholders to do the same.

Content management and editorial responsibility of the project website: WP6 leader – Plantpress.

ECHO website

1.6.3 Social media

Social media activities are crucial to motivate new groups of citizen scientists or other stakeholders to join the project. Can be also useful to inform about events and milestones.

We decided not to set up a project account on Twitter due to the rise of offensive content. Moreover, the application after rebranding and changing its name to X is read by the algorithms of some browsers as not safe

Our social media platforms of first choice are the following:

- Facebook: ECHO Horizon Europe Project
- LinkedIn: ECHO Horizon Europe Project

Posts will be published in a minimum number of **10/month**. For the first phase of the project, the social media accounts will share posts related to the project scope and objectives to build a community of interest, creating an audience for when there are project results to share. The social media accounts will be managed by Plantpress with support from the partners.

ECHO partners are encouraged to repost ECHO content on their social media and make sure **to use the hashtags**:

#echosoilproject #echosoil #soil #missionsoil #horizonEU #soilhealth #savesoil

#citizenscienceContent related recommendations

Social media communication should always have a distinct message and a clear writing style. The use of emojis can help reduce the danger of misinterpretation and can convey the tone of the conversation or a feeling about a message. They should not be seen as a gimmick, or unscientific, but rather as a way to add nuance and be inclusive.

Here are some good examples:

Photos and Videos

ECHO Partners are encouraged to think beyond words and consider how pictures, graphics, charts, and video or audio clips can play a part in our communication activities. They are easily shared via social media, which can capture the attention of people that might otherwise not stumble across our project. Using high quality pictures and short, good quality videos will generate greater interest among our audience.

The pictures we take ourselves are the most valuable to us and give the best idea about the project. This includes photos of our activities, as well as the environment we are aiming to improve and protect - both the soil, and its end-users. Use alternatively a picture, video, GIF, infographic, link or poll for variation of content. Directions on how to properly showcase EU visibility are included in project communication and visibility toolbox.

We encourage ECHO partners to produce their own videos in order to promote the project. Videos should get to the point quickly to catch people's attention. Short interviews with beneficiaries and stake holders can be attractive additions to web pages/e-newsletters/social media. We are aiming to produce a series of short videos from different countries called "testimonials" of people of different ages, from different backgrounds, joining ECHO.

1.6.4 Language

Whether communicating online, through printed media, or face-to-face, the language we use – its terminology, tone, and complexity – matters. This is especially significant in citizen science projects. Common words used in science need to be adapted to audiences from different cultural or literal backgrounds, and the tone should never be authoritative. Texts should be easily understandable, even to someone new to the topic. We should avoid using acronyms in our communications, especially those which might be confusing to non-specialists, and always explain what the scientific terminology means in the context of our project.

1.6.5 Storytelling

During the implementation of the project Partners will be often asked to briefly present the project (interviews or events).

We suggest each Partner prepare their version of 2-3 key messages which are short, simple and give a clear idea of what it is about. They should be flexible enough to be used across all communication tools frequently and consistently.

Answer the questions:

Why do you do what you do?

We are an organization operating in...

That is why participation in the project dedicated to soil health is important to us.

What challenge do you face?

Soil is a vital, yet often disregarded, resource that supports life on Earth by providing the foundation for agriculture, forests, and various other natural ecosystems. However, soil degradation is a growing concern around the world, and it can have severe consequences for our

planet like reduced crop yields, increased greenhouse gas emissions, and decreased biodiversity. ECHO aims to prevent this by bringing together citizens and volunteer scientists from around Europe to work towards a common goal of protecting and preserving our soils, thus contributing to the transition towards healthy soils of the EU Mission: “A Soil Deal for Europe”.

What is the benefit of the project?

ECHO will generate new data on the health status of EU soils, complementing existing soil mapping and monitoring in EU Member States, including the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO). The project will develop and deploy 28 tailor-made citizen science initiatives across EU Member States, taking into account different land-uses, soil types, and biogeographical regions, as well as stakeholder needs.

Call for action/why care about this issue?

We believe that the ECHO project will have a significant impact on soil health and citizen engagement across the EU and become an important step towards protecting and preserving our soil for future generations. By working together, we can ensure that our soil remains healthy and productive, and that we continue to enjoy the many benefits it provides. To learn more about the project and how you can get involved, visit our website or contact us directly.

1.6.6 Newsletter

We will issue a newsletter periodically (2/year) to inform target groups of project progress and will contain information on project events, available results and products. It will have a direct connection to the project website and social media network. The newsletters will be published on the ECHO website and promoted through social media.

1.6.7 Publications

While designing and producing any publications such as leaflets, brochures, newsletters etc., these rules should be followed:

- It should be by default disseminated in electronic form and only where appropriate or necessary in paper version with best environmental practice in mind.
- Remember to acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate)

	UK Research and Innovation	
Project: ECHO - Engaging citizens in soil science: the road to healthier soils Funded by the European Union under GA no. 101112869 – ECHO and co-funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).		
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2. Dissemination

2.1 Objectives

Dissemination is focused on making the project results accessible to other potential users outside the consortium. It aims to transfer and circulate knowledge to the ones who can make the best use of it and further build on the project's results to maximise the impact.

Dissemination is also important for increasing the visibility of the project.

Partners should keep track of all their dissemination, publication and exploitation activities during project implementation. They will be partially available on the website and used in reporting on the project activities.

2.2 Stakeholder and target groups

The dissemination strategy is to promote the project results and outcomes towards the target groups of ECHO, those involved in citizen science initiatives as well as end-users, using the citizen science generated data:

- **Citizens:** members of citizen science initiatives including students, youth groups, women's groups, farmers, foresters, environmental conservation groups and associations (including NGOs), urban food and growing associations, city greening initiatives)
- **End-users:** farmers, land managers of agricultural soils, land managers and users of urban and peri-urban soils, initiatives and users of soil health data related to food quality, forest managers and other users of forest soil data, scientists, private companies, educators, and other institutions responsible for soil management, policy and decision making)

2.3 Media relations

To reach the general public with the principles and results of the project, cooperation with the mainstream media will be established. Mass media are a good option for target groups with a larger number of people (such as the general public). We encourage all Partners to consider what is your target group while choosing appropriate channels: online or paper media, local or larger audience etc. Inviting media representatives to events also does not usually require any additional costs.

When sending a press release, consider the following points:

- Write an engaging headline
- Get straight to the point (save background information to the end)
- Use easy language and keep the release short
- Tell a story: give a face to the story and tell the journalist what the story means to their audience (for example: tell about a person whose life has been impacted by the project)
- Provide resources like photos, videos and interview opportunities

- Remember to mention the financiers and required visibility elements to the press release
- Add contact information for further information

A proposal:

ECHO Project Aims to Engage, Empower and Enable EU Citizens to Improve Soil Health

We are excited to announce the launch of the project “ECHO - Engaging Citizens in soil science: the road to Healthier Soils”, a groundbreaking initiative aimed at increasing knowledge and awareness of soil health among EU citizens. The project is based on three main principles: engaging citizens, empowering them with knowledge and an active role in data collection, and enabling them to participate in decision-making on soil issues.

Soil is a vital, yet often disregarded, resource that supports life on Earth by providing the foundation for agriculture, forests, and various other natural ecosystems. However, soil degradation is a growing concern around the world, and it can have severe consequences for our planet like reduced crop yields, increased greenhouse gas emissions, and decreased biodiversity. ECHO aims to prevent this by bringing together citizens and volunteer scientists from around Europe to work towards a common goal of protecting and preserving our soils, thus contributing to the transition towards healthy soils of the EU Mission: “A Soil Deal for Europe”.

ECHO will generate new data on the health status of EU soils, complementing existing soil mapping and monitoring in EU Member States, including the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO). The project will develop and deploy 28 tailor-made citizen science initiatives across EU Member States, taking into account different land-uses, soil types, and biogeographical regions, as well as stakeholder needs. With 16 participants from all over Europe, including 10 leading universities and research centres, 4 SMEs, and 2 Foundations, under the coordination of the Free University of Bolzano-Bozen, ECHO will assess 16,500 sites in different climate and biogeographic regions to achieve its ambitious goals.

We believe that the ECHO project will have a significant impact on soil health and citizen engagement across the EU and become an important step towards protecting and preserving our soil for future generations. By working together, we can ensure that our soil remains healthy and productive, and that we continue to enjoy the many benefits it provides.

To learn more about the project and how you can get involved, visit our website or contact us directly.

ECHO is a Research and Innovation Action funded by the European Union, under the GA 101112869, Program Horizon Europe topic HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-09. The project started on June, 1st 2023 and will last 4 years. The ECHO consortium consists of 16 participants: 10 leading universities and research centres (Free University of Bolzano-Bozen, University of Hohenheim FCIENCIAS.ID and University of Lisboa, University of Bologna, The James Hutton Institute, University of Eastern Finland American Farm School, University Stefan Cel Mare Suceava, University of Extremadura), 4 SMEs (Solutopus, Plantpress, Quanta Labs, Ambienta), and 2 Foundations (Ibercivis, Resoil). The participants from small companies and foundations, as business and civil society representatives, are complementary to the soil and social sciences experts of academic partners and crucial for achieving the ambitious goals of ECHO.

2.4 Events and publications

Project partners will attend national and international conferences relevant for the scope of ECHO to reach the scientific community (Table 5, 6). ECHO will publish in open-access peer reviewed journals. ECHO will also foresee popular publications to reach a wider audience and/or specific end-users.

Table 5. Non-exhaustive list of suitable conferences, events and journals for ECHO outputs.

Conferences/Events	Journals
Public Communication of Science and Technology	Science Communication
European Citizen Science Association International Conference	Citizen Science: Theory and Practice
European Conference on Education	Soil Science Research
World Congress of Soil Science	Geoderma, Geoderma Regional
CtiSciConference organised by the Citizen Science Association	Frontiers in Earth Science
ENGAGE Conference	Journal of Applied Ecology
The Festival of the New European Bauhaus	Ecology Letters
EuroSoil congress	Plant and Soil
Global Soil Biodiversity Conference	Applied Soil Ecology

Table 6. Non-exhaustive list of the conferences and events of ECHO partners' interest

Partner	Event name	Location
Plantpress	AGROTECH - Trade fair	Kielce, Poland
Hutton	Doors Open Festival	Dundee, Scotland
Re Soil	Festival della scienza	Genova, Italy
Re Soil	Monferrato Green Farm	Casale M.to, Italy
Re Soil	Re Soil	Re Soil
FC.ID	Frontier in E3	Lisbon, Portugal
FC.ID	4º Encontro Nacional de Ciência Cidadã (ENCC2023)	Coimbra, Portugal
UHOH	European Bioeconomy Scientific Forum 2023	Vienna, Austria
UNIBIZ	Festival Le Mille e una Scienza	Bolzano, Italy
AFS	87th Thessaloniki International Fair	Thessaloniki International Trade Fair- Exhibition, Greece
Re Soil	States General for soil health, Ecomondo	Rimini, Italy
University Sefan Cel Mare	Integrated Management of Environmental Resources (IMER Conference)	Suceava, Romania

2.5 Synergies with other projects

Establishing synergies to maximise the impact of ECHO communication and dissemination activities requires the alignment of efforts from ongoing initiatives that are supporting the Soil Mission priorities. Specifically, these synergies capitalise on the developments of EC initiatives where the ECHO consortium has a strong experience and has links related to R&I.

ECHO will initiate alliances with other projects funded under the Soil Mission calls (such as: SoilWise, Benchmark, NBSoil, HuMUS) and outreach to other ongoing European activities, such as corresponding European Innovation Partnership (EIP) operational groups. This will be a continuous task throughout the project lifetime to ensure that project results will be widely taken-up and extended. This includes the production of at least 10 EIP practice abstracts in the common format, identification of events suitable for participation, and the identification of opportunities for collaboration and co-design, such as joint stakeholder events, webinars, and information materials. ECHO will regularly deliver insights and results into the EU's Mission Implementation Platform launched as a tender by the REA. Furthermore, we will establish regular contact, monitor progress, create synergies and generate substantive opportunities for cross-fertilisation of ideas with project(s) funded under the MISS-2021-SOIL-02-02 call (Validating and further developing indicators for soil health and functions")

2.6 Key Performance Indicators for dissemination activities

- Scientific open access publications in journals (>8)
- Outreach publications (2/year)
- Participation to conferences and events (10/year)
- Networking and joint activities with related projects and initiatives, training, and competence and capacity building for citizens focusing on young people
- **28 co-creation workshops** to engage citizens
- **9 co-creation workshops** to engage end-users
- **1 policy workshop** at EU level during green week in Brussel.

3. Exploitation

3.1 Objectives

Exploitation focuses on making concrete use of research results for commercial, societal, and political purposes and can only start once the project results are available. Depending on the nature and scope of the project, there is a wide spectrum of results that may be recognised as exploitable, including policy recommendations or standardisation activities. ECHO will deliver 7 results with specific means of verification and KPIs listed in table 7.

Table 7. Key performance indicators for ECHO results.

Results	Means of verification	Quantitative target
RP 1 Pan-European map of target citizen groups	A map of citizen groups	28 European countries (Member States plus Scotland) covered
	Citizens groups	Each identified group is expected to involve at least 75 citizens.
RP 2 Citizen engaged with soil health activities	One-to-one meetings with citizen groups	30 meetings throughout the project's lifetime
	Interactive workshops and targeted presentations	A minimum of 28 activities throughout the project's lifetime
RP 3 Soil stewardship across Europe	Citizen initiatives	>20 % of engaged citizens are expected to participate in soil stewardship efforts
	Co-creation workshops	28
RP 4 Citizen science platform	The user-friendliness and feasibility of the toolbox	500 scientists involved in the testing - collect and analyse soil data
	Guidelines and protocols translation	Translation in 24 official European languages
RP 5 Increased knowledge among citizens about soil health	Pre-/post attitude and knowledge surveys	16500 - corresponding to the citizens involved in ECHO initiatives
RP 6 Increased knowledge about soil health amplifying scientific research	Soil samples analysed as a result of ECHO	16500 – 28 Citizen Science initiatives x 590 sites sampled on average per initiative
	Soil health data indicators measured <i>on-site</i>	8 (presence of pollutants, soil organic matter, soil structure, soil biodiversity, soil pH, vegetation cover, landscape heterogeneity, forest cover)
	Soil health data indicators measured <i>off-site</i>	2 (bacterial and fungal biodiversity and heavy metal concentration)
RP 7 Long-term digital data repository	Validation of the all software stacks	Functional (e.g., integration testing, interface testing, regression testing) and non-functional testing (e.g., load testing, recovery testing).

	User testing	At least 5 experts engaged and volunteer end-users
RP 8 Different end-users groups engaged	Number of end-users contacted	Through a survey (200) through interviews (50)
	Number of end-user groups engaged	1 per country, 1/end-user groups representing the most influential end-uses of citizen science generated data
	Engagement strategy and guideline document	2000 downloads
RP 9 Showcase the utility of citizen science data on soil health	Identification and engagement current and potential end-users of citizen science	1 focus group per consortium country
	EU-level workshop to demonstrate to and inform policymakers and farmer communities, current and potential benefits linked to the use of citizen science generated soil health data.	1 in Brussels in connection with the EU Green Week

The main aim of project ECHO's exploitation plan is to ensure the results deliver the expected impact during and after the project, supported by the dissemination and communication plan. The exploitation of the results will take place in compliance with the EU provisions on Open Science. Furthermore, Table 8 outlines the exploitation of the research outcomes by the ECHO partners. As part of the exploitation strategy, Table 9 recommends potential exploitation of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) by a wide range of stakeholders, at different levels. All ECHO partners are actively involved in exploiting the results.

The key exploitable results of ECHO can be grouped into four main thematic clusters:

- iv. Result 1: Pan-European map of target citizen groups and Result 2: Citizen engaged with soil health activities;
- v. Result 3: Soil stewardship across Europe and Result 4: Citizen science platform;
- vi. Result 5: Increased knowledge among citizens about soil health and Result 6: Increased knowledge among scientists about soil health amplifying scientific research;
- vii. Result 7: Long-term digital data repository, Result 8: Different end-users groups engaged and Result 9: Showcase of the utility of citizen science data on soil health.

Table 8. Exploitation of research outcomes by ECHO partners

Thematic cluster	Result	Who	How
Thematic cluster 1	Result 1: Pan-European map of target citizen groups	All partners expect QUANTA and AMBIENTA	The identification of target citizen groups, their training and engagement will ensure their participation to citizen science initiatives (Table 1.2.2), partners can exploit their increased awareness about soil health for further soil-related activities, projects and collaborations.
	Result 2: Citizen engaged with soil health activities		
Thematic cluster 2	Result 3: Soil stewardship across Europe	All partners	The training of expert citizens on soil health will generate new soil-related initiatives across Europe. The citizen science platform will be a great tool to further generate soil health data and could be exploited for future activities, projects beyond the life of ECHO .
	Result 4: Citizen science platform		
Thematic cluster 3	Result 5: Increased knowledge among citizens about soil health	UHOH, UNIBO, FC.ID, CIENCIAS, SOLUTOPUS, IBE, UEF, AFS, RESOIL	The increased knowledge on soil health among citizens will guarantee their engagement in protecting and maintaining soil health creating new opportunities and innovative measures for citizen involvement – during the project with participation in citizen science initiatives and beyond the project guaranteeing the interest of citizens in soil health for future activities.
	Result 6: Increased knowledge among scientists about soil health amplifying scientific research	UNIBZ, FC.ID, CIENCIAS, HUTTON, USV, UEF, AFS, UEX	The scientific partners will acquire unique soil health data fostering the better understanding of complex interactions between soil properties. The outcome of ECHO will generate a holistic overview of European soils to develop new avenues of collaborative research.
Thematic cluster 4	Result 7: Long-term digital data repository	All partners	Availability of European soil health data for further usage. It will enable the development of new data products and services that require long-term soil health data and go beyond traditional services such as dashboards. For example, long-term digital data objects can be used to develop projections in the context of interdisciplinary models and digital twins. In addition, these new services will impact different stakeholders by allowing them to investigate what-if scenario analyses in their scope.
	Result 8: Different end-users groups engaged	UNIBZ, UHOH, FC.ID, CIENCIAS, SOLUTOPUS, UEF,	Engagement of end-users will encourage public participation in planning decisions in soil related issues.
	Result 9: Showcase of the utility of citizen science data on soil health	UNIBO, UHOH, UEF, AFS, UNIBZ, HUTTON	

Table 9. Exploitation of research outcomes by stakeholders

Result	KER	Description	Potential Exploitation	KPIs for Exploitation (Post-Project)
Result 1: Pan-European map of target citizen groups	Stakeholder Engagement Matrix	A matrix of various identified citizen groups (communities) across Europe interested in soil health and related activities	It can be used by researchers, policymakers, other European projects and NGOs in order to design new soil health (or other environmental) initiatives.	The matrix remains publicly accessible in Zenodo under CC-BY licenses The matrix is referenced in at least 5 new citizen science projects
Result 2: Citizen engaged with soil health activities	Stakeholder Engagement Strategy	A structured engagement methodology outlining methods to involve diverse stakeholders in soil health monitoring through soil data collection and analysis.	It can be used in future Horizon Europe and national research projects to ensure effective citizen science engagement. It could be adopted by NGOs, environmental agencies, and research institutions for stakeholder-driven environmental initiatives. Provides a best-practice model for citizen engagement in large-scale EU-funded projects.	At least 3 EU-funded projects adopting the engagement methodology. At least 2 organizations (NGOs, agencies, research bodies) implementing the methodology.
Result 3: Soil stewardship across Europe	Soil stewardship pathways and impact stories	A curated set of real-life stories and role models emerging from the ECHO pilots, highlighting the journeys, practices, and community contributions of engaged citizens who adopted soil stewardship behaviours. These narratives serve as inspiration and guidance for future adopters	Used by NGOs, community groups, and local institutions to showcase the practical impact of citizen engagement in soil health, motivate new participants, and illustrate long-term benefits	Referenced in at least 2 awareness campaigns or community engagement programmes.

Result 4: Citizen science platform	Participatory Technologies for Soil Observations	A co-designed digital infrastructure for citizen science soil data acquisition, curation, and visualization.	Adopted by NGOs, land managers, and researchers for long-term citizen engagement in soil monitoring. Integrated into soil management training programs. Forms the foundation for future digital citizen observatories.	Used in at least 5 environmental citizen science programs after project completion. >10,000 users engage with the platform annually post-project. At least 3 external citizen science platforms adopt the participatory technologies model.
Result 5: Increased knowledge among citizens about soil health	(Pre-/post) surveys to assess attitude, knowledge and behavior	A survey incorporating three newly developed psychometric scales, to be administered at three time points, to assess the impact of the project on citizens' soil knowledge, attitudes in the form of connectedness to soil and sustainable soil behaviors.	It can be used by researchers and other future European projects in order to effectively assess the social impact of similar initiatives at the participant level.	At least 3 research projects utilizing the newly developed psychometric scales for assessing soil health knowledge, connectedness to soil, and sustainable soil behavior The developed psychometric scales cited in at least 5 peer-reviewed publications.
	Report on increased knowledge among citizens about soil health	A report (and likely a scientific publication) describing the findings regarding changes in citizens' soil health knowledge (as well as attitudes and behavior) before and after the citizen science initiatives.	The findings can inform scientific research, policy and future Horizon Europe projects about the effectiveness of citizen science in enhancing important individual outcomes (e.g., sustainable soil behavior), necessary for achieving the goals of the Mission Soil.	At least 3 projects or programs incorporating the projects' findings in their development At least 5 citations of the projects' findings in peer-reviewed publications.

Result 6: Increased knowledge among scientists about soil health amplifying scientific research	Increased knowledge among scientists	Scientists and citizens will gain access to new soil health data from diverse European regions	This data can support new scientific research, interdisciplinary collaborations, and improved soil monitoring frameworks and also can lead to policy support	At least 5 scientific publications using citizen-contributed soil data.
Result 7: Long-term digital data repository	EOSC Integration & Open Science Adoption	ECHOREPO will be connected to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), ensuring broad accessibility of soil health data.	Research institutions can freely access and analyze soil health data. Encourages new research and commercial applications based on ECHO data. Provides an open-source model for digital soil monitoring systems.	At least 3 new research projects use the EOSC-integrated data. >500 downloads of open-source components supporting the repository. At least 5 citations in peer-reviewed publications within 3 years post-project.
Result 8: Different end-users groups engaged	Stakeholder co-creation reports	Reports summarising the outcomes of co-creation workshops and consultations with diverse user groups (e.g., farmers, planners, public authorities), documenting needs, expectations, and feedback on data use and soil health strategies.	Provides a foundation for future participatory planning efforts and ensures the citizen science approach aligns with real-world policy and land management needs.	Referenced in 2+ external land-use or policy planning projects.
Result 9: Showcase of the utility of citizen science data on soil health	Impact briefs and list of domains	A list of domains of real-world use cases where ECHO citizen science data contribute to improved decision-making, awareness-raising, or innovation in soil health management.	Used as an advocacy tool by institutions, researchers, and NGOs to promote citizen science and justify investment in participatory monitoring	Cited in 5 or more reports or policy briefs related to citizen science or soil health.

It is worth emphasizing the special exploitation value of **ECHOREPO – long-term digital data repository**.

Most of the current citizen observatories are highly biased towards reporting observations in areas such as biodiversity and not soil. Therefore, they do not provide a robust cyber-infrastructure delivering a digital repository and interfaces specifically oriented to reporting and consulting soil-related information. ECHOREPO-CI (digital repository cyber-infrastructure) contributes to the project by developing a scalable, highly available, and comprehensive cyber-infrastructure delivering a long-term repository to facilitate the reporting, sharing, and consulting of soil information. This would enable the consolidation of a larger community of scientists, the general public, and end-users for activities to support the assessment of European Soil health.

ECHOREPO will be fuelled by soil health data of 8 indicators plus soil biodiversity data (bacterial and fungal diversity) and heavy metal concentration entries provided by the 28 citizen science activities across Europe addressing different soil types and biogeographical regions (up to 16500 sites).

3.2 IPR Management

Throughout ECHO's implementation and beyond, the consortium will address IP issues and questions such as those raised by the European IP Helpdesk's recommendations on the successful valorisation of knowledge and research results and its Guide to Intellectual Property Management in Horizon Europe. The project Consortium Agreement regulates questions of intellectual property and innovation management in Articles 8 – Results; 9 – Access Rights; and 10 – Non-disclosure of information. ECHO thus adopts a comprehensive IP Management strategy that reflects the needs of a collaborative *open* and *fair* citizen science project.

As such, ECHO's workplan relies on open and inclusive knowledge building and sharing processes. From the start of the project, background has been identified by all beneficiaries and associated partners and access to specific background may be subject to legal restrictions or limits, as set out in the Consortium Agreement.

Deliverables and exploitable results will be made public – as open as possible and as closed as necessary – under gold open access rules and Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) copyright license, for which anyone will be permitted to adapt, remix, distribute and build upon the project's results, even for commercial use, as long as the source is properly cited, in compliance with the EU copyright legislation. Nevertheless, to protect IP, prior notice of any planned project publication shall be given to the ECHO beneficiaries and associated partners at least 21 calendar days before the publication, as laid out in further detail in the Consortium Agreement, Article 8.4.

Ownership of results will also be handled in accordance with the Consortium Agreement provisions and project results will continuously be monitored for newly generated knowledge and related new IP. Beneficiaries will furthermore profit from participation in IP training activities

and from European Commission funded support services, such as the European IP Helpdesk, Horizon IP Scan, and the Horizon Results Booster.

A Results Ownership List will further clarify the responsibilities of the respective owners for the exploitation of their project results beyond its conclusion.

3.2.1 Individual IP Profiles

A tailored and individual (per partner) analysis (questionnaire) will be implemented resulting in the development of an individual IP Profile. Based on this profile, the status of each partner will be mapped in terms of project innovations and internal processes, while we can group project partners in terms of maturity.

3.2.2 IP protective tools and measures

In terms of IP Protection, ECHO will establish the tools and mechanisms to facilitate informed decision-making by all partners regarding the potential protection of their IP. ECHO will identify and propose IP protective measures, on partner's needs, as well as based on different technologies, end-products etc. that will be generated in the project. Capacity Escalation Activities will also take place based on partners needs and preferences (questionnaire).

3.2.3 IP Protection results - beyond funded period

Confidentiality obligations, results transfer, obligations to protect results capable of commercial exploitation are considered also after the end of the project. ECHO workplan relies on open and inclusive knowledge building and sharing processes. All deliverables and exploitable results will be made public under gold open access rules and Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) copyright license, for which anyone will be permitted to adapt, remix, distribute and build upon the project's results, even for commercial use, as long as the source is properly cited, in compliance with the EU copyright legislation.

3.2.4 Ownership of Results

Results are owned by the Party that generates them.

3.2.5 Joint ownership

Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 16.4 and its Annex 5, Section Ownership of results, with the following additions:

Unless otherwise agreed:

- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research and teaching activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s).
- each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise Exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license), if

the other joint owners are given: (a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and (b) fair and reasonable compensation.

The joint owners shall agree on all protection measures and the division of related cost in advance.

3.2.6 Transfer of Results

- Each Party may transfer ownership of its own Results, including its share in jointly owned Results, following the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 16.4 and its Annex 5, Section Transfer and licensing of results, sub-section “Transfer of ownership”.
- Each Party may identify specific third parties it intends to transfer the ownership of its Results to in Attachment (3) of this Consortium Agreement. The other Parties hereby waive their right to prior notice and their right to object to such a transfer to listed third parties according to the Grant Agreement Article 16.4 and its Annex 5, Section Transfer of licensing of results, sub-section “Transfer of ownership”, 3rd paragraph.
- The transferring Party shall, however, at the time of the transfer, inform the other Parties of such transfer and shall ensure that the rights of the other Parties under the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement will not be affected by such transfer. Any addition to Attachment (3) after signature of this Consortium Agreement requires a decision of the General Assembly.
- The Parties recognise that in the framework of a merger or an acquisition of an important part of its assets, it may be impossible under applicable EU and national laws on mergers and acquisitions for a Party to give at least 45 calendar days prior notice for the transfer as foreseen in the Grant Agreement. In this case, notice of the transfer will be given as soon as possible and in any case not later than 30 (thirty) days after the transfer.
- The obligations above apply only for as long as other Parties still have - or still may request - Access Rights to the Results.

Examples of graphic materials:

I. ECHO word document template

II. ECHO presentation template

A long, scientific title of the presentation

a presentation by You

Łódź, Poland
April 1st, 2023

ECHO ENGAGING CITIZENS IN SOIL SCIENCE: THE ROAD TO HEALTHIER SOILS

Co-funded by the European Union

UK Research and Innovation

Funded by the European Union under GA no. 101112869 - ECHO and co-funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union, UKRI nor the REA can be held responsible for them.

III. ECHO leaflet

WHY IS ECHO IMPORTANT?

Soil is a vital, yet often disregarded, resource that supports life on Earth by providing the foundation for agriculture, forests, and various other natural ecosystems. However, soil degradation is a growing concern around the world, and it can have severe consequences for our planet like reduced crop yields, increased greenhouse gas emissions, and decreased bio-diversity.

The Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' recognizes an urgent need for research and innovation to protect and restore soil health via sustainable interventions. To achieve this ambitious goal requires knowledge and awareness of the importance of long-term soil health, its value and challenges combined with the drivers across Europe to accomplish the transition towards healthy soils by 2030.

ECHO aims to enhance existing, and create new, knowledge through amplification of novel scientific research and increasing awareness and literacy of soil health related issues. ECHO will lead and develop coordinated citizen science initiatives across European Member States considering different land-uses and stakeholder needs.

PARTNERS

unibz, RE SOIL FOUNDATION, ibercivis, SOLUTEPUS, ambienta, CIÊNCIAS ULISBOA, AMERICAN FARM SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF SATEEN FINLAND, USU, PLANTPRESS, Quanta Labs, The James Hutton Institute, UNIVERSITY OF HOHENHEIM, FCiências, EX

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UK Research and Innovation

HORIZON EUROPE Project
Research & Innovation
June, 1st 2023 – May, 31st 2027

ECHO ENGAGING CITIZENS IN SOIL SCIENCE: THE ROAD TO HEALTHIER SOILS

IV. ECHO roll-up

Funded by the European Union

UK Research and Innovation

HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT:
RESEARCH AND INNOVATION
JUNE 2023 - MAY 2027

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ENGAGING CITIZENS IN SOIL SCIENCE:
THE ROAD TO HEALTHIER SOILS

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THE ROAD TO HEALTHIER SOILS

